

EDUCATION IN VISUAL COMMUNICATION DESIGN STUDIES IN THE AGE OF GLOBALIZED KNOWLEDGE

Prof. Dr. Emin Dogan AYDIN

Chairman

Visual Communication Design Department

Faculty of Communication

Yeditepe University

SYSTEMOLOGY AND EPSTEMOLOGY AS THE BASES FOR THE VISUAL COMMUNICATION DESIGN

Barriers in Communication

Basic Disciplines Related to HCI

- ▶ Computer Engineering
- ▶ Cognitive Psychology
- ▶ Social and Organizational Psychology
- ▶ Ergonomics and Human Factor
- ▶ Basic Engineering Sciences
- ▶ Design
- ▶ Anthropology
- ▶ Sociology
- ▶ Philosophy
- ▶ Linguistics
- ▶ Artificial Intelligence

Basic Disciplines Related to HCI

Basics of Human - Computer Interaction

The main goals of the VCD graduate program

- ▶ To offer graduates who are well informed about global developments in a variety of arts and communications technology and who have a strong creative incentive backed with a complete theoretical background.
- ▶ To inform the participants about the theories of arts, aesthetics, visual culture, informatics, general systems and cybernetic methods, and to instruct them about the rapid changes and the impacts of communications with regard to technology, dimension and content, within the framework of deduction theories.
- ▶ To give a notion of the social, cultural and economical implications of any creative activity and its relation to the existing body of universal art in order to give the student a wide perspective over their own work
- ▶ To instruct about the planning, functioning, processing and structure of information and communication systems. To teach the appropriate manners of utilization to come up with the best possible design options.
- ▶ To instruct about the social and economic utilization of the general system, structures and data-sources, communication systems /organizations / vehicles / channels and networks in society.

The main goals of the VCD graduate program

- ▶ To teach the terms and concepts about the information systems and the description of the databases and databanks which are permanently accumulated and updated in a large scale; and to scrutinize over their application areas and utilization in the functioning of informatics.
- ▶ To study various research and innovation projects in order to find solutions to the different application fields and practical informatics functions in an independent and critical approach; and to supply expertise on system analysis and synthesis.
- ▶ To supply information, related to the planning, innovation, application and integration of the international applications and practicing of information sciences.
- ▶ To obtain the understanding of the problems and efforts related to the security and completion of the information sciences /networks / and data.
- ▶ To evaluate and find out solutions about one dimensional information flow, and technological, cultural, political and legal dependency in the world.
- ▶ To supply information about the technological transfer from the point of view of functional signs its choice and application.

Thank you for your time...

Prof. Dr. Emin Dođan AYDIN